

Schools of Empirism

**Perspectives on Central European mining regions of the Early
Modern Age as laboratories of modern knowledge cultures**

by

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Abstract:

Recent research emphasizes that empiricist approaches already emerged long before the seventeenth and eighteenth century. While many of these contributions focus on specific professions, it is the aim of this article to supplement this discourse by describing certain social spaces that fostered empiricist attitudes. A particularly interesting example in this respect is the mining region of the Erzgebirge (Saxony) in the fifteenth and sixteenth century. The following article will use this mining district as a kind of historical laboratory, as a space not only for scientific observation but also as a structure within which specific forms of knowledge were socially tested, to show how the economic transformation of this region supported the rise of characteristic elements of empiricist thinking. It is common practice to link the appraisal of useful knowledge, (personal) experience and the distrust towards (scholastic) authorities in those days with only small minorities. By addressing not only the struggles of the commercial elites but also the challenges of the average mining-town resident, this paper tries to add to this view by demonstrating how entire masses of people inhabiting the late medieval Erzgebirge were affected by and schooled to think in empiricist ways.

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*There are more things in heaven and earth, Horatio,
Than are dreamt of in your philosophy.*

- Shakespeare: *Hamlet* (1.5.167-8), Hamlet to Horatio

1. Introduction: An empirical science

The rise and the formation of modern economic thought in the seventeenth and eighteenth century is often connected with a newly emerging ethos of positive, methodologically validated and, above all, *empirically founded knowledge*.¹

William Petty (1623-1687), according to Karl Marx, Joseph Schumpeter and many others,² one of the major figures in the development of the newly emerging political economy, famously wrote in the introduction of his posthumously published *Political Arithmetic* (1690): *"I have taken the course [...] to use only arguments of sense, and to consider only such causes, as have visible foundations in nature; leaving those that depend upon the mutable minds, opinions, appetites, and passions of particular men, to the consideration of others [...]."*³

Like many of his contemporaries, Petty was very much concerned with the question of the *reliability of knowledge*. In particular, late medieval and early modern transformations of society had turned this topic into a much contemplated issue. Innovations like the printing press, which had drastically lowered the cost of spreading one's own opinion over great distances,⁴ but also the growing importance of markets were drivers of this process, leading, among others, to a strong awareness of features like trustworthiness, credit and truthfulness⁵ - of people, as much as their (written) statements.

This insecurity concerning claims and utterances of others proved especially unsatisfactory for scholars like William Petty who, following in the footsteps of the

¹ H.D. Kurz, *Geschichte des ökonomischen Denkens*, Munich 2017, p.22ff.

² For an overview compare T. McCormick, *William Petty and the ambitions of political arithmetic*, Oxford and New York 2009, p.1, fn. 2.

³ W. Petty, *Political Arithmetic*, Glasgow 1690, p.IX.

⁴ P. Burke, *Papier und Marktgeschehen. Die Geburt der Wissensgesellschaft*, Berlin 2000, p.125ff.

⁵ C. Muldrew, *Zur Anthropologie des Kapitalismus*, in: *Historische Anthropologie*, Vol. 6, No. 2, 1998, pp. 167-199; C. Muldrew, *Hard food for Midas: Cash and its social value in early modern England*, in: *Past and Present*, Vol. 170, No. 1, 2001, pp. 78-120.

much admired Francis Bacon (1561-1626),⁶ thought of knowledge as a means of empowerment, as a *useful* tool to foster the common good of humankind as well as to strengthen Sovereign and Kingdom. The so called modern philosophers of the late sixteenth and seventeenth century, however heterogenic in their overall ideas and concepts,⁷ were rather united in thinking about knowledge as a kind of – potentially and ideally - productive and effective knowledge,⁸ which was useful in order to understand, control and transform natural and societal phenomena.

The realm of mere subjective opinions had therefore to be left behind, to the same extent as - on the other side of the spectrum - the sterile book-wisdom and deductive reasoning of the scholastic tradition, which was then still dominating European universities.⁹ Typical semantics of empiricist thinking like the idea of *useful knowledge*, the *distrust towards scholastic authorities* and the praise of (*personal*) *experience* can thus be regarded as outcomes and carriages of such an effort. They allowed for an ostensible independence for its practitioners, for a scientific gaze that was supposedly neither contaminated by the subjective opinions of the many nor hindered by scholastic conventions, a perspective which would claim to be able and ready to *actively* get in touch with things.

Empiricism is often commonly associated with authors from the seventeenth- and eighteenth-century like John Locke (1632-1704) - a contemporary of William Petty - , George Berkeley (1685-1753) or David Hume (1711-1776). However, recent literature has pointed out to the fact that individuals, groups or professions (for example Renaissance artists and artisans) had cultivated variants of empirical approaches and semantics long before the Enlightenment era.¹⁰

The following article wants to add to this discussion by showing how local transformations in the social fabric were able to trigger the creation of social spaces in which empiricist attitudes became increasingly common – long before scholars like William Petty would start to advocate similar concepts. While many historical accounts in the history of the sciences used cities, regions or countries as rather indifferent backgrounds, it will be the aim of this article to show how the particularities of a place, its structures and practices, influenced and enabled certain forms of epistemology and knowledge. The intention of such an account of practice is to shift away the attention

⁶ A. Roncaglia, *The Wealth of Ideas. A History of Economic Thought*, Cambridge (UK) and New York 2005, p.56.

⁷ S. Shapin (2017), *Die wissenschaftliche Revolution*, Frankfurt/Main 2017, p.14 ff.

⁸ P.H. Smith (1994), *The Business of Alchemy. Science and Culture in the Holy Roman Empire*, Princeton 1994, p.33 ff; P.H. Smith (2004), *The Body of the Artisan. Art and Experience in the Scientific Revolution*, Chicago 2004, p.18.

⁹ L. Daston, *Wunder, Beweise und Tatsachen*, Frankfurt/Main 2001, p.49.

¹⁰ The literature concerning this topic is vast. For an overview within the history of ideas see P. Lipton, Article: Empiricism, History of, in: *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 2001, pp. 4481-4485, p.4482; For a prominent example within the history of knowledge see Smith, *The Body*; For an earlier but still important approach to this topic see E.Ziesel, *Die sozialen Ursprünge der neuzeitlichen Wissenschaft*, Frankfurt/Main 1976.

from dis-embedded geniuses, certain groups (like artisans) or certain eras (like the Renaissance) as creators and media of empiricist epistemologies – and instead to emphasize the role of *knowledge cultures*¹¹ in the invention and proliferation of certain practices to acquire and legitimize knowledge.

An especially interesting case in this context, which will be developed over the next several pages, were the Middle-European mining regions of the fifteenth and sixteenth century, in particular the Erzgebirge in Saxony (Germany): an environment in which not only “modern” semantics of profit, risk and trust,¹² but in particular the before mentioned *elements of empiricist thinking* played a major role in various discourses. Much of the structural and societal circumstances that have been described above in the context of the new philosophy of the Enlightenment era, the tension between demands for effective and productive knowledge on the one hand, the struggle with the interestedness and subjectivity of people’s utterances and the inaptness of scholastic sources on the other, can already be found here in an early and condensed form.

Two interlinked aspects about this knowledge culture are particularly worth considering – and will hence form the core topic of this article. First, the example of the late-medieval and early-modern Erzgebirge seems to suggest a certain *relationship between economy and knowledge*. It appears that when markets grow in importance for social reproduction and, often a result of the very same process, reach a strong level of anonymity among market-participants, the need for useful and reliable *empirically founded* information among them will increase significantly. The epistemology in demand in such economized areas, argued in the last chapter, seems to be of a specific type: it is *selective* rather than *holistic*, *restless* rather than *contemplative*. Additionally, the case of the Erzgebirge strongly emphasizes the great extent to which local societies might have been affected by such epistemological transformations. It was, this text will argue, by no means only the upper class, aristocrats, intellectuals or commercial elites which were confronted with questions of the reliability of information, the role of experience and the senses or the general usefulness of knowledge but also the common people who had to navigate through highly commercialized waters. The economy of the Erzgebirge and the daily life connected to it became, according to this thesis, a *school of empiricism* – teaching people how to behave, how to value and to acquire different forms of knowledge and information.

¹¹ The term „knowledge culture“ can be described as *„a set of historically developed and contingent practices, mechanisms and principles, which define - within a certain place and time - what is and can be (legitimately) known. Knowledge cultures generate and validate knowledge“* - K. Knorr-Cetina, *Wissenskulturen*, Frankfurt/Main 2002, p.11.

¹² T. Asmussen, Glück auf! Fortuna und Risiko im Frühneuzeitlichen Bergbau, in: *FKW//Zeitschrift für Geschlechterforschung und visuelle Kultur*, Nr. 60, 2016, pp. 30-41.

The structure of the following chapters serves to illustrate and elaborate these two dimensions. While the former is rather latent in the course of the text, eventually to be discussed and to be summarized in the *last chapter*, the latter is going to be addressed in two separate sections: the *second and upcoming chapter* sketches cultural changes within the realm of the marketplace (due to supply requirements of the mining population) that heighten the principal value of information and experience for the broad populace. The *third chapter*, now shifting the focus to the upper end of the social hierarchy, will turn to the world of societal elites, to mining investors, their characteristic struggles with information deficits and to the genre of mining books (*Bergbücher*) in which we can observe an *empiricist ethos* which emerged as a reaction to the specific risks of pit shareholders.

2. A people of empiricists: The montane-market of the senses

The fourteenth- and early fifteenth-century have often been described as a period of great depression of the Middle-European mining sector. Although new research indicates that the general condition of the industry was, considering different territories and ores, much more diverse than initially thought, the theses of decline still holds for the mining on precious metals, especially in the traditional centers of the industry such as the Erzgebirge in Saxony.¹³

After a first silver mining-boom in the area of the later city of Freiberg (founded next to the newly discovered places of silver recovery around 1168 by the margrave Otto from Meissen)¹⁴ in the twelfth-century, it took the pitmen only a little more than a century to reach depths between 160 and 200 meters.¹⁵ Silver in the Erzgebirge is normally found in so called ore lodes, stone crevices filled with barren minerals and silver ore, forcing the miners to work their way steeply into the ground, quickly reaching levels of depth that would not be necessary elsewhere.¹⁶ These circumstances created a row of problems for the industry. Masses of groundwater were entering the pits and had to be dealt with while the exchange of men and materials between underground and surface also had to

¹³ With some generally accepted exceptions concerning the production of tin, iron and calamine – C. Bartels/L. Klappauf, *Das Mittelalter. Der Aufschwung des Bergbaus unter den karolingischen und ottonischen Herrschern, die mittelalterliche Blüte und der Abschwung bis zur Mitte des 14. Jahrhunderts*, in: K. Tenfelde/ S. Berger / H.-C. Seidel (Ed.), *Geschichte des deutschen Bergbaus, Vol. 1: Der alteuropäische Bergbau. Von den Anfängen bis zur Mitte des 18. Jahrhunderts*, Münster 2012, pp.111-248. p.238f; I. Burghardt, *Der Edel- und Buntmetallbergbau im meißnisch-sächsischen Erzgebirge (1350-1470). Verfassung - Betriebsorganisation - Unternehmensstrukturen*, Dresden 2018 (Veröffentlichungen des Landesamtes für Archäologie Sachsen, 64).

¹⁴ W. Herrmann, *Bergbau und Kultur. Beiträge zur Geschichte des Freiburger Bergbaus und der Bergakademie*, Berlin 1953, p.13.

¹⁵ Bartels/Klappauf, *Das Mittelalter*, p.239f.

¹⁶ O. Wagenbreth, *Zur Herausbildung der Montanwissenschaften in Sachsen im 16. Jahrhundert*, in: *Sächsische Heimatblätter*, Vol. 32, No. 2, 1985, pp. 56-62, p.57.

be organized. The feudal structure of montane-production, based on the concept of the working mine owner (*Eigenlehner*), privately or in small groups financing and managing the business (and paying rents to the sovereign), could not keep up with these growing difficulties.¹⁷ Lack of capital was holding back technological innovation, recurring incidents of the plague were pushing the prices of workforce, difficult (cold and rainy) weather-conditions were fostering the intrusion of water into the pits¹⁸ - all these variables led, particularly in the course of the fourteenth-century, to the decay of most of the silver-mines in the Erzgebirge region.

Eventually, beginning in the fourteenth and then increasingly noticeable in the fifteenth century, started a process that gradually led to a division of capital and labor. Growing numbers of pit shareholders did not work on site anymore but merely invested money into the enterprise.¹⁹ Economic developments on an European scale had led to a significant accumulation of bourgeois funds, especially in the important commercial towns of Upper Germany (above all in Nuremberg and Augsburg) but also in Saxonia (e.g. Leipzig), which were now entering the montane-industry of the Erzgebirge.²⁰ Together with the growing awareness of the Wettin Princes that mining for silver might be an ideal instrument to augment their riches, these developments meant major improvements in the mining sector were only a matter of time.²¹ New machines and drainage tunnels were installed, Pits were bailed and – a fortunate consequence of both luck and deliberately deployed means for exploration²² – extraordinarily promising silver-sites were found.

In 1446 silver-ore was found in the area of today's Schneeberg, with the major breakthrough taking place in 1470. Around 1490 more silver was discovered at Glashütte and the soon to be founded Annaberg. More discoveries, and hence additional mining-towns, followed: 1500 Brand close to Freiberg, 1501 Buchholz, 1513 Hohenstein, 1521 Marienberg, 1522 Scheibenberg and 1526 Oberwiesenthal (and so forth).²³ Rumors (*Berggeschrey*) of unheard-of silver-findings flowed through the whole of the Holy Roman Empire and attracted masses of people from often faraway places which quickly transformed small settlements into (by the standards of the time) towns of considerable

¹⁷ A. Laube, *Studien über den Erzgebirgischen Silberbergbau von 1470 bis 1546*, Berlin 1974, p.82; J. Köhler, *Die Keime des Kapitalismus im Sächsischen Bergbau (1168 bis um 1500)*, Berlin 1955, p.53ff.

¹⁸ *Bartels/Klappauf*, *Das Mittelalter*, p.239.

¹⁹ H. Bräuer, *Armut in Bergstädten des sächsischen Erzgebirges während der frühen Neuzeit*, in: K.H. Kaufhold/ W. Reininghaus (Ed.), *Stadt und Bergbau*, Köln 2004, pp. 199-238, p.203.

²⁰ Laube, *Studien*, p.5.

²¹ *Ibid.*, p.9f; P.O. Long, *The Openness of Knowledge: An Ideal and its Context in 16th-Century Writings on Mining and Metallurgy*, in: *Technology and Culture*, Vol. 32, No. 2, Part 1, 1991, pp. 318-355, p.324.

²² *Ibid.*, p.14f.

²³ K. Blaschke, *Sachsen im Zeitalter der Reformation*, in: *Sächsische Heimatblätter*, Vol. 13, No. 4, 1967, pp. 145-192, p.160f.

size (Joachimsthal for instance grew within only two decades to the size of Bologna or Prag at the time, with almost 18000 inhabitants).²⁴ Thousands of people of many stations and origins, experienced miners as well as craftsmen, castoff monks and farmers, many of them „strange, raw and unmanageable people“,²⁵ betook themselves ‚just as though on a pilgrimage‘²⁶ to the barely populated hills of the Erzgebirge and began to hack up the soil.²⁷

The district of Schneeberg alone produced in the years between 1470 and 1483 the almost unbelievable yield of 2.8 billion guilder²⁸ (in comparison: a year's salary of a hewer in the Erzgebirge was in those days around 25 guilder). Other mines, as the ones of Annaberg, could, after some glorious findings at the end of the fifteenth century, still reach peak yields of 112,230 (in 1517) and 333,465 (in 1537) in the decades to come.²⁹ Although many lost their fortunes or even their lives in the mines, some, even amongst the lower classes, made it to tremendous riches³⁰ - enough to nourish the myths that travelled the lands: already in the first half of the sixteenth-century the population of the Erzgebirge reached approximately 50,000 – 70,000 inhabitants,³¹ which at that point was considerably more than the number of people living in the biggest German city Cologne for example, with around 35,000 residents (around 1500).³²

Feeding the Mountains

It is no surprise that these demographic developments created enormous problems concerning the supply and provision with all kinds of goods, in particular with foodstuff. While other major commercial centers of this time like Flanders, Paris and

²⁴ E. Westermann, Zur Versorgung von Bergbaurevieren: Aufgaben künftiger Forschungen, in: E. Westermann (Ed.), Bergbaureviere als Verbrauchszentren im vorindustriellen Europa (Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte, Supplement No. 130), Stuttgart 1997, pp. 429-442, p.434.

²⁵ O. Hoppe, Der Silberbergbau zu Schneeberg bis zum Jahre 1500, Freiberg 1908, p.10.

²⁶ L. Bönhoff, Petrus Albinus. Annabergische Annales de anno 1492 bis 1539, in: Mitteilungen des Vereins für Geschichte von Annaberg und Umgegend, XI, 1910, pp.1-50, p.11 – cited after S. Karant-Nunn, Between Two Worlds. The Social Position of the Silver Miners of the Erzgebirge, c. 1460-1575, in: Social History, Vol. 14, No. 3, 1989, pp. 307-322, p.309f.

²⁷ Karant-Nunn, Two Worlds, p.309f.

²⁸ Bräuer, Armut, p.201.

²⁹ W. Lorenz, Leben und Wirken des Adam Ries in der Bergstadt Annaberg, in: Sächsische Heimatblätter, Vol. 31, No. 1, 1985, pp.5-8, p.5.

³⁰ S. Sieber, Zur Geschichte des erzgebirgischen Bergbaues, Halle (Saale) 1954, p.30.

³¹ U. Schirmer, Ernährung im Erzgebirge im 15. und 16. Jahrhundert. Produktion, Handel und Verbrauch, in: R. Aurig / S. Herzog/ S. Lässig (Ed.), Landesgeschichte in Sachsen. Tradition und Innovation, Bielefeld 1997, pp. 129-144, p.130; M. Straube, Notwendigkeiten, Umfang und Herkunft von Nahrungsmittellieferungen in das sächsische Erzgebirge zu Beginn des 16. Jahrhunderts, in: Westermann, E. (Ed.), Bergbaureviere als Verbrauchszentren im vorindustriellen Europa (Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte, Supplement No. 130), Stuttgart 1997, pp. 203-220.

³² R. Wittmann, Geschichte des deutschen Buchhandels, Munich 2011, p.39.

London could draw much of their needed agricultural products from their direct environment³³, this proved to be almost impossible for the towns of the Erzgebirge.³⁴ The conditions for growing crops were particularly bad. Stony surfaces, high erosion levels, steep slopes and only 130-140 days without frost per annum made survival difficult even for the farmers living in this area.³⁵ Small gardens to grow vegetables, sometimes fruit trees, normally a handful of chickens, rabbits or even a goat (frequently called “miners-cow” in these regions) that belonged to the small *oeconomia* of the average miner family (and presumably most other residents of the Erzgebirge) could, under such climatic and geologic circumstances, not be more than supplements to the daily diet.³⁶ Time to invest into side-occupations was scarce anyhow. Women and children were often working too,³⁷ while most of the men, following the incremental spread of wage labor in the montane-business and the introduction of the eight-hour shift in the fifteenth century,³⁸ spend much of their free time digging for ores on their own accounts (*Weilarbeit*).³⁹

Of course, not all residents of the Erzgebirge were miners – on the contrary. Current research on the early modern mining-industry in Rettenbach (Tirol/Austria) proves that while only 86 miners actually worked in the pit, still over 1,152 persons were directly depending on this economy.⁴⁰ So called “*Anschnitte*” (i.e. quarterly pit-registers, summarizing all earnings and spendings) show the impressive variety of materials, machines and services that were needed to run mining-operations back then.⁴¹ Consequently, the mining-boom in the Erzgebirge did not just attract pitmen but people from all kinds of professional backgrounds. Owing to this diversity, its catchment area

³³ R. Unger, Thresholds for Market Integration in the Low countries and England in the Fifteenth Century, in: L. Armstrong/ I. Elbl/ M. Elbl (Ed.), Money, Markets and Trade in Late Medieval Europe, Leiden and Boston 2007, pp. 349-382, p.350ff; A. Everitt, The marketing of agricultural produce, 1500-1640, in: J. Chartes (Ed.), Agricultural markets and trade 1500-1750, Cambridge (UK) 1990, pp. 15-156, p.63ff; F. Braudel, Sozialgeschichte des 15. – 18. Jahrhunderts, Part 2: Der Handel, Munich 1986, p.31.

³⁴ Despite a settlement-movement of new incoming farmers around 1500 – H. Löscher, Die bäuerliche Nachbesiedlung des Erzgebirges um 1500, in: Blätter für deutsche Landesgeschichte 91, 1954, pp. 130–157.

³⁵ W. Kaulfuß, Zustand, Nutzung und Ertragsleistung der Agrarflächen des Osterzgebirges, in: Sächsische Heimatblätter, Vol. 13, No. 4, 1968, pp. 154-162, p.154ff.

³⁶ G. Heilfurth, Bergbaukultur im Erzgebirge. Grundzüge und Auswirkungen (Reihe Weiss-Grün 5), Dresden 1995, p.19.

³⁷ J. Schreiter, Frauen im Erzbergbau – dargestellt am Beispiel des Erzgebirges. Eine Analyse des Forschungsstands, in: W. Ingenhaeff/J. Bair (Ed.), Bergbau und Alltag, Hall (Tyrol)/ Vienna 2008, pp.257-278, p.269.

³⁸ Köhler, Keime, p.65.

³⁹ R. Dietrich, Untersuchungen zum Frühkapitalismus im mitteldeutschen Erzbergbau und Metallhandel, Hildesheim 1991, p.189.

⁴⁰ R. Tasser, Vor- und Nachteile des Knappenlebens in vier Jahrhunderten. Dargestellt am Beispiel Pettau, in: W. Ingenhaeff/J. Bair (Ed.), Bergbau und Alltag, Hall (Tyrol)/Vienna 2008, pp. 31-58, p.36f.

⁴¹ C. Bartels, Drei Fallstudien zum Betriebsmittelverbrauch bedeutender Oberharzer Zechen im 16., 17. und 18. Jahrhundert. Quellenbefunde, Hypothesen, Fragestellungen, in: E. Westermann (Ed.), Bergbaureviere als Verbrauchszentren im vorindustriellen Europa (Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte, Supplement No. 130), Stuttgart 1997, pp. 145-174, p.148ff.

became clearly subject to a strong impulse towards increased levels of differentiation and specialization of professions⁴² - which implies, among others, that even the group of non-miners possessed only minor temporal resources for any agricultural occupation on the side.

Taking all these aspects into consideration, it becomes obvious that the Erzgebirge community was not only unable to feed itself⁴³ – but also unable to provide itself with most materials for its flourishing crafts and hence for the “conspicuous consumption” (Thorstein Veblen) of a growing middle class⁴⁴ as well as for the demands of the mining businesses. In the Erzgebirge, *high demands met considerable purchasing power* – on the family level of miners and craftsmen⁴⁵ as well as on the level of investors, factors and (frequently investors themselves) civil servants of the Saxon princes. Uwe Schirmer calculated that approximately 11,000 tons of wheat that had to be transported,⁴⁶ herds of pigs and sheep along with around 15,000 to 18,500 oxen from Poland and Russia were to be transported every year into the mountains.⁴⁷ Horses, an indispensable asset to the whole economic region for road-transports,⁴⁸ agricultural chores as well as for the strenuous logistics within the pit-operations⁴⁹ had to be imported from as far as Brandenburg, Pomerania, Friesland and Denmark.⁵⁰ But also salt and spices, books and scripts, cloth, jewelry, metal wares of all kinds and other goods had to find and found

⁴² R. Jäpel, *Handwerk, Gewerbe und Handel im Westerzgebirge des 16. Jahrhunderts*, in: H. Zwahr/ U. Schirmer/ H. Steinführer (Ed.), *Leipzig, Mitteldeutschland und Europa*, Beucha 2000, pp. 339-348, p.339.

⁴³ Considering the fact that a person consumed on average between 200 kg ungrounded wheat per annum along with (e.g.) 4 kg of lard, 50 kg of meat and between 300 and 400 liters of beer – U. Dirlmeier, *Die Ernährung als mögliche Determinante der Bevölkerungsentwicklung*, B. Herrmann/ R. Sprandel (Ed.), *Determinanten der Bevölkerungsentwicklung im Mittelalter*, Weinheim 1987, pp. 143-154, p.153f; Straube, *Notwendigkeiten*, p.216; V. Groebner, *Ökonomie ohne Haus. Zum Wirtschaften armer Leute in Nürnberg am Ende des 15. Jahrhunderts*, Göttingen 1993, p.102.

⁴⁴ Dietrich, *Frühkapitalismus*, p.187.

⁴⁵ Schirmer, *Ernährung*, p.132. There were, however, great differences of income in between different professions within the mining business (e.g. miners and smelters) and in between different levels of training (e.g. apprentice and full hewer) – Bräuer, *Armut*, p.211.

⁴⁶ Schirmer, *Ernährung*, p.140f.

⁴⁷ A. Bingener, Andreas / C. Bartels / M. Fessner, *Die große Zeit des Silbers. Der Bergbau im deutschsprachigen Raum von der Mitte des 15. bis zum Ende des 16. Jahrhunderts*, in: K. Tenfelde/ S. Berger / H.-C. Seidel (Ed.), *Geschichte des deutschen Bergbaus*, Vol. 1: *Der alteuropäische Bergbau. Von den Anfängen bis zur Mitte des 18. Jahrhunderts*, Münster 2012, pp.317-452, p.324 – an impressive number considering the fact that one of the biggest cattle-market of central Germany of these days, Buttstädt, processed only between 8000 and 12000 cows per annum – U. Schirmer, *Der ober- und westdeutsche Schlachtviehbezug vom Buttstädter Markt im 16. Jahrhundert*, in: *Jahrbuch für fränkische Landesforschung*, Vol. 56, 1996, pp. 259-282.

⁴⁸ Straube, *Notwendigkeiten*, p.213f.

⁴⁹ Even small mining-districts had to deploy over a hundred horses for their daily operations, including a high loss rate of these animals – N. Hirschmann, *Zum bergbaulichen Verbrauchszentrum Oberpfalz im 16. Jahrhundert*, in: E. Westermann (Ed.), *Bergbaureviere als Verbrauchszentren im vorindustriellen Europa* (Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte, Supplement No. 130), Stuttgart 1997, pp.59-84.p.70ff; U. Schirmer, *Das spätmittelalterlich-frühneuzeitliche Erzgebirge als Wirtschafts- und Sozialregion (1470-1550)*, in: M. Schattkowsky (Ed.), *Das Erzgebirge im 16. Jahrhundert. Gestaltwandel einer Kulturlandschaft im Reformationszeitalter*, Leipzig 2013, pp. 45-76, p.50.

⁵⁰ U. Schirmer, *Das Amt Grimma 1485 bis 1548*, Beucha 1996, p.322-324.

their way to the montane-markets.⁵¹ What had come into existence here was a type of society which was very unusual for its time (and centuries to come),⁵² a society fully depending on the supply of goods for its daily needs,⁵³ *a society that was entirely depending on markets, or respectively marketplaces, to (re-) produce itself.*⁵⁴

This is not to imply that markets were irrelevant for the (then by and large)⁵⁵ rural and thinly populated areas of Europe. On the contrary it is often suggested today that already in central and late medieval times a close-meshed network of market opportunities covered most of its territories.⁵⁶ Unreliable harvests and hence volatile grain supplies and -prices,⁵⁷ limits of a farm's productive capabilities in volume and variety⁵⁸ (which were in many places intensified by processes of increasing social differentiation concerning the ownership of land)⁵⁹ and a growing demand of authorisations for money rather than labor- or natural rents made markets an important building brick of these societies, too. They were, however, *not more than a supplement* to these communities. Most of these markets were - as the production of surpluses was neither big nor reliable - very small in size, comprising of only a handful of wagons or stalls and manageable assortments, characterized by low levels of anonymity between the small groups of market participants (which mainly stemmed from the village/small-town and its direct surroundings) and with an emphasis on, also due to persistent

⁵¹ For the richness and variety of foodstuffs consumed in the Erzgebirge of these days see also *C. Herbig*, Archäobotanische Untersuchungen, in: *M. Schubert/ M. Wegener*, Die Grabung „Roter Hirsch“. Erste Ergebnisse zur hochmittelalterlichen Siedlung der Dippoldiswalder Bergleute in: in: *R. Smolnik (Ed.)*, ArchaeoMontan 2014. Ergebnisse und Perspektiven. Internationale Fachtagung Dippoldiswalde 23. bis 25. Oktober 2014, Arbeits- und Forschungsberichte zur sächsischen Bodendenkmalpflege, Vol. 29, 2014, pp. 195–203.

⁵² *R. Dülmen*, Kultur und Alltag in der frühen Neuzeit, Vol. 2 Dorf und Stadt 16. – 18. Jahrhundert, Munich 1992, p.38; *P. Kriedte*, Spätféudalismus und Handelskapital, Göttingen 1980, p.37.

⁵³ *Straube*, Notwendigkeiten, p.206.

⁵⁴ Schirmer describes it as a *total marked-dependency* („völlige Marktabhängigkeit“) – *Schirmer*, Ernährung, p.132

⁵⁵ *G. Hardach/ J. Schilling*, Das Buch vom Markt. Eine Wirtschafts- und Kulturgeschichte, Luzern and Frankfurt/Main 1980, p.120.

⁵⁶ *M. Fenske*, Marktkultur in der Frühen Neuzeit, Köln 2006, p.2 and p.44f; *Everitt*, The marketing, p.47; *F. Irsigler*, Messen, Jahrmärkte und Stadtentwicklung in Europa. Mittelalter und frühe Neuzeit, in: *F. Irsigler/ M. Pauly (Ed.)*, Messen, Jahrmärkte und Stadtentwicklung in Europa, Trier 2007, pp. 1-24, p.8 and *M. Pauly*, Jahrmärkte in Europa vom 14. bis zum 16. Jahrhundert. Regionale Untersuchungen und der Versuch einer Typologie, in: *F. Irsigler/ M. Pauly (Ed.)*, Messen, Jahrmärkte und Stadtentwicklung in Europa, Trier 2007, pp. 25-40, p.29.

⁵⁷ *Groebner*, Ökonomie, p.65 and p.72f.

⁵⁸ *Hardach/Schilling*, Markt, p.93f – This problem was in reality often enhanced by ongoing specialization processes within the agricultural domain of many countrysides. – *S. Sonderegger/ A. Zangger*, Zur Deckung des bäuerlichen Konsumbedarfs in der Ostschweiz im Spätmittelalter, in: *J. Tanner/ B. Veyrassat/ J. Mathieu/ H. Siegrist / R. Wecker (Ed.)*, Geschichte der Konsumgesellschaft. Märkte, Kultur und Identität (15. – 20. Jahrhundert), Zürich 1998, pp. 15-34, p.24.

⁵⁹ Already in the fifteenth century creating a growing class of rural residents with (almost) no land property – cottagers, lodgers, day laborer and alike – *R. von Friedeburg*, Die ländliche Gesellschaft um 1500. Forschungsstand und Forschungsperspektiven, in: Zeitschrift für Agrargeschichte und Agrarsoziologie, Vol.1, No.51, 2003, pp.30-42, p.39; *Dülmen*, Kultur, pp.16-28.

“*bullion femines*” in the fifteenth-century,⁶⁰ personal credit- rather than cash-transactions.⁶¹

The majority of the marketplaces in the direct drawing zones of the montane-industry and population of the Erzgebirge were clearly of another type. Here, market and industry/population were *existentially intertwined* – if one side of this relation failed or ceased to exist, so did the other.⁶² Layouts of many of the mining-towns that were then conceptualized and realized, impressively symbolize this relationship – implementing, against the zeitgeist of city planning (which was very much focused on the defensive-/fortress-character of town-architecture)⁶³, *huge marketplaces* (see Illustration 1) in the center of these new towns, sometimes (in case of unsuccessful mining towns like Platz or Platten)⁶⁴ far bigger in size than the whole rest of the settlement.⁶⁵

⁶⁰ P. Spufford, *Money and its use in medieval Europe*, Cambridge (UK) and New York 1989; J. Day, *The Great Bullion Famine of the Fifteenth Century*, in: *Past and Present*, Vol. 79, Issue 1, 1978, pp. 3-54.; J. Le Goff, *Geld im Mittelalter*, Stuttgart 2011, p.19; M. North, *Das Geld und seine Geschichte: Vom Mittelalter bis zur Gegenwart*, Munich 1994, p.38.

⁶¹ Muldrew, *Anthropologie*; Muldrew, *Hard food*; G. Clemens (Ed.), *Schuldenlast und Schuldenwert. Kreditnetzwerke in der europäischen Geschichte 1300-1900* (Trierer Historische Forschungen 65), Trier 2008; J. Schlumbohm (Ed.), *Soziale Praxis des Kredits. 16. – 20. Jahrhundert*, Hannover 2007.

⁶² A typical governemental topos of these days is the fear of officials that if market-rights might not be granted the montane-businesses of an area might falter – Laube, *Studien*, p.19; while there are, on the other side of the equation, several recordings from complaints of local populations that after the decline of their pits also their markets have collapsed – Bräuer, *Armut*, p.216f.

⁶³ R. Eaton, *Die ideale Stadt*, Berlin 2001, p.59.

⁶⁴ K. Kratzsch, *Bergstädte des Erzgebirges. Städtebau und Kunst zur Zeit der Reformation* (Münchner Kunsthistorische Abhandlungen IV), Munich and Zurich 1972, p.51.

⁶⁵ Marienberg was designed in 1521 with a 130 on 130 meter (sic!) marketplace (almost the size of the famous *Les Halles* (Paris) when first established by King Philip of France in 1183), Jöhstadt 1518 with a market the size of 140 on 70 meters, Neustadt (Wiesenthal) 1527 with a market the size of 100 on 100 meters (et cetera) – Kratzsch, *Bergstädte*, p.43f and p.52f.

Illustration 1: Mining towns and their large markets. The layout from (to the left) Sebastiansberg (1530) and (to the right) Neustadt im Wiesenthal (1527)⁶⁶

Empiricism of a market society

Along with the size of these markets, just as was the case in most of the commercial centers and major towns elsewhere (earlier as well as later), it is reasonable to expect a specific form of (modern) market-culture - a *marketplace of empiricists* - to prevail.

A central concern of marketplace regulations of these days affected access rights of strangers (customers as well as merchants).⁶⁷ Sometimes strict rules forbade the entry entirely, or limited selling and purchasing to clear-cut times,⁶⁸ spaces (within the zone of the marketplace)⁶⁹ and variants of transactions (trade in-between strangers for example was often forbidden)⁷⁰ —it was not unusual to already define fellow craftsmen or farmers from neighboring villages and towns as “foreigner”.⁷¹ This protectionist philosophy clearly did not function (with such rigor) for bigger markets and fairs, just as it did not, as several records indicate, for most of the montane-markets which had (as elaborated) to satisfy a comparatively high demand.⁷²

⁶⁶ The illustrations are drawn from *Kratzsch, Bergstädte*, p.51.

⁶⁷ *Dülmen, Kultur*, p.85,

⁶⁸ *Hardach/Schilling, Markt*, p.91.

⁶⁹ *W. Freitag, Städtische Märkte in der mittelalterlichen und frühneuzeitlichen Stadt*, in: *L. Morscher/ M. Scheutz/ W. Schuster (Ed.), Orte der Stadt im Wandel vom Mittelalter zur Gegenwart*, Innsbruck 2013, pp.39-58, p.51f.

⁷⁰ *Irsigler, Messen*, p.19; *W. Held, Zwischen Marktplatz und Anger*, Weimar 1988, p.98.

⁷¹ *Fenske, Marktkultur*, p.53ff; *H. Bräuer, Chemnitz zwischen 1450 und 1650: Menschen in ihren Kontexten*, Chemnitz 2005, p.109f.

⁷² *S. Kazimier, Zur Versorgung mittelslowakischer Bergstädte mit Nahrungsmitteln und anderen Verbrauchsgütern vom 14. bis zum 18. Jahrhundert*, in: *E. Westermann (Ed.), Bergbaureviere als Verbrauchszentren im*

With rising numbers of participants in general and increasing amounts of foreigners in particular, the *degree of reciprocal anonymity* inevitably grew, too. Under the commercial circumstances of these centuries – which applied to the whole of Europe as much as to the Erzgebirge region – with its predominantly low standardization of goods, measures and weights, in combination with the high volatility of currency-values (due to Gresham's Law and additional regulation-deficits also the case in silver-rich Saxony),⁷³ such transformations induced market-cultures that were strongly characterized by *universal insecurity* and *information-problems* of all involved market players.⁷⁴ This opened up a gap of nescience which invited new possibilities – for buyer as well as sellers – to outsmart, trick and deceive each other. Laurence Fontaine consequently defines “uncertainty” (*Unwägbarkeit*) as *the* characteristic feature of these kinds of markets,⁷⁵ a property which in turn makes the search for “usable signs, clues to how particular matters at the immediate moment specifically stand”⁷⁶ (concerning the particular wares in regard) *the* decisive and focal activity within this competitive realm.

The spatial organization of the marketplace (e.g. placing similar products next to each other for better comparison), the patterns of clientelization, the role of credit (reputation), public opinion and the rituals of bargaining were altogether cultural forms that both tried to limit, but also to exploit this universal uncertainty.⁷⁷ These institutionalized structures were therefore rather paradoxical in nature, trying to serve two entirely contrary ends (commercial control and freedom) at the same time – which made personal capacities, *especially market-experience and ready senses, intelligently deployed, all the more important.*

The knowledge that made a person successful in these larger marketplaces was nothing to be found in the texts of *scholastic authorities*, nor was it in any way a kind of pragmatic situation that could have been effectively and comprehensively controlled by a singular

vorindustriellen Europa (Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte, Supplement No. 130), Stuttgart 1997, pp. 295-306, p.299f; A. Westermann, Zentralität und Funktionalität. Überlegungen zur Bedeutung der Bergbauorte in den Vorderösterreichischen Montanregionen der Frühen Neuzeit, in: K.H. Kaufhold/ W. Reininghaus (Ed.), Stadt und Bergbau, Köln 2004, pp. 73-92.

⁷³ P.R. Rössner, Die (proto-)globalen Spannungsfelder und Verflechtungen mitteldeutscher Münz- und Währungspolitik um 1500. Das Beispiel der sächsischen Talerprägung, in: M. Schattkowsky (Ed.), Das Erzgebirge im 16. Jahrhundert. Gestaltwandel einer Kulturlandschaft im Reformationszeitalter, Leipzig 2013, pp. 103-158, p.103ff.

⁷⁴ F.S. Fanselow, The Bazaar Economy or How Bizarre is the Bazaar Really?, in: Man, New Series, Vol. 25, No. 2, 1990, pp. 250-265, p.252ff; Fenske, Marktkultur.

⁷⁵ L. Fontaine, Bemerkungen zum Kaufen als soziale Praxis, in: Historische Anthropologie, Vol. 14, No. 3, 2006, pp. 334-348, p.334.

⁷⁶ C. Geertz, Suq: the bazaar economy in Sefrou, in: C. Geertz/ H. Geertz/ L. Rosen (Ed.): Meaning and order in Moroccan society, Cambridge 1979, pp. 123-314, p.216.

⁷⁷ Ibid., p.217.

theoretical effort.⁷⁸ The trick was (only) to know what you *needed to know*, to collect *reliable* data for your own transactions, while in contrast, aiming for the knowledge of “everything” was (regarding the big markets with all their goods, participants and daily dynamics) impossible to achieve and, a heresy in the context of over a thousand years of philosophic tradition, economically *useless*.

To these ends it was imperative to empirically learn about the real workings of a practice, to learn how to not only use the inner (*sensus communis*, memory and imagination) but also the five external senses (which were by and large heavily mistrusted by the theology of these days as “portals of sin”⁷⁹).⁸⁰ The problem later proposed by the already mentioned authors Francis Bacon (see for example his *idols of marketplace*)⁸¹ and William Petty, of how to discern between true and false, between the manifold signs that reach our attention, finds its archetypical situation here: these marketplaces represented an extremely dense sensory experience,⁸² an array of hundreds of more or less subtle signals that had to be carefully “read” and evaluated by the individual – *a task which could only be mastered through repeated practice and advice on how to see, hear, smell, touch and taste*.

Back then, particularly in the late middle ages and early modern times, a considerable corpus of books and scripts came into existence, providing merchants, factors but also members of wealthy households (including service personal) with useful knowledge concerning customs of trade and rules of the marketplace(s) – helping them to deal with the before mentioned problems of large and rather anonymous fields of economic transaction.⁸³ From Northern-Italian *Zibaldoni*⁸⁴ (a kind of merchants-notebook for personal use or for the instruction of family members) of the thirteenth century- to *Manuali* (handbooks respective of standard texts for the broader community of merchants) of the fifteenth century,⁸⁵ from the anonymously published *Ménagier de Paris*

⁷⁸ It is very interesting to compare these practical conditions and their implications for knowledge cultures with later representations of knowledge in economic thought – for example the works of Friedrich Hayek, e.g. *F. Hayek*, The Use of Knowledge in Society, in: *The American Economic Review*, Vol. 35, Issue 4, 1945, pp. 519-530.

⁷⁹ *R.G. Newhauser*, Introduction: The Sensual Middle Ages, in: *R.G. Newhauser (Ed.)*, *A Cultural History of the Senses*, Vol. 2: In the Middle Ages, London and New York 2014, pp. 1-22, p.9.

⁸⁰ *E. Welch*, The Senses in the Marketplace: Sensory Knowledge in a Material World, in: *H. Roodenburg (Ed.)*, *A Cultural History of the Senses*, Vol. 3: In the Renaissance, London and New York 2014, pp. 61-86, p.64.

⁸¹ Compare *New Organon*, aphorism 43.

⁸² *M. Carlin*, The Senses in the Marketplace: Markets, Shops, and Shopping in Medieval Towns, in: *R.G. Newhauser (Ed.)*, *A Cultural History of the Senses*, Vol. 2: In the Middle Ages, London and New York 2014, pp. 67-88, p.67f.

⁸³ *S. Schmidt*, Kommunikationsrevolution oder Zweite Kommerzielle Revolution?, in: *M. Häberlein/ C. Jeggle (Ed.)*, *Praktiken des Handels*, Konstanz 2010, pp. 245-282, p.252.

⁸⁴ *P. Spufford*, Spätmittelalterliche Kaufmannsnotizbücher als Quelle zur Bankengeschichte. Ein Projektbericht, in: *M. North (Ed.)*, *Kredit im spätmittelalterlichen und frühneuzeitlichen Europa*, Köln und Wien 1991, pp. 103-120.

⁸⁵ *M. Denzel*, Handelspraktiken als wirtschaftshistorische Quellengattung vom Mittelalter bis in das frühe 20. Jahrhundert. Eine Einführung, in: *M. Denzel/ J.C. Hocquet / H. Witthöft (Ed.)*, *Kaufmannsbücher und Handelspraktiken vom Spätmittelalter bis zum 20. Jahrhundert*, Stuttgart 2002, pp. 11-46, p.18.

(1393) – amongst various other texts advising on which markets to attend and how to discern between good and bad products - to John Browne's *the Marchant's Avizo* (1587) and many others to come. The metamorphosis of the market culture within the sphere of commercial centers (as the late medieval and early modern Erzgebirge) adds to this already well known observation a second aspect: *it was by far not only the upper classes that had to adapt their epistemology, their frames and habits to the economization of these days, but the entire society of these flourishing economic zones.* The rise of the markets taught them a new way of thinking, turning places such as the Erzgebirge into *schools of empiricism*: long before modern natural philosophy acquired influential status, maybe even preparing the ground for the later success of its ideas, these areas conveyed a specific form of knowledge culture to the masses, a culture with (among others) a particular relation to the senses, to the utility of knowledge, to abstract theories and the traditional wisdom of authorities.

The next chapter will, despite the long literary tradition of Manuali, Zibaldoni (etc.), informing us of the empiricist and practical values within merchant-culture (and alike),⁸⁶ investigate into comparable epistemological changes on the level of the *commercial elites*. The reason behind this is not merely the prominent role of venture capital in the mining-boom or the strong influence that wealthy investors had on the transformation of local Saxon living environments, but the possibility to demonstrate, by using the then mining-industry as an *historical laboratory*,⁸⁷ that virtually everyone that dared to invest into the montane-business – this included clergy as well as Wettin Princes – got drawn in and infected by an empiricist ethos.

3. The struggle with empty words and the empirical ethos of mining-investors

The previously mentioned Francis Bacon (1561-1626), paragon of William Petty and of much of modern science to come, was known to be a staunch critic of scholasticism, of scholastic thought and practice. The latter would "*hunt more after words than matter*"⁸⁸, indulging in empty sophistry, creating not only "*minds empty and unfraught with matter*"⁸⁹

⁸⁶ H. Lang, Wissensdiskurse in der ökonomischen Praxis. Kaufmannbankiers als Experten der Märkte im 16. Jahrhundert, in: M. Füssel/ P. Knäble/ N. Elsemann (Ed.), Wissen und Wirtschaft. Expertenkulturen und Märkte vom 13. bis 18. Jahrhundert, Göttingen 2017, pp. 141-168..

⁸⁷ In the sense of both an observational and experimental space. This concerns the dimension of the scientific spectator as much as the dimension of the individuals within the area that is being observed.

⁸⁸ F. Bacon, The Works, Vol. III, ed. by J.Spedding/R.Ellis/D.Heath, London 1887, p.283.

⁸⁹ Ibid., p.326.

but also an empty and sterile (scientific) language – abstract, without empirical content (matter) and hence *useless* for society.

The following generation of philosophers like Descartes, Leibniz, Hobbes or Locke will eventually take up this thread of argument, combine it with nominalist concepts, and make language itself a subject and object of science. Language came to be *the* essential instrument to construe and amalgamate the world,⁹⁰ which rendered it at the same time both a dangerous and useful tool, critical for personal insight as much as for corrections of the social body⁹¹ and (political-) economical processes. Empty or imprecise words, inapt or insufficient vocabulary, poor or degenerated languages (not to speak of its ability to deceive and decoy persons) came to be a decisive factor for the success (or failure) of individual aspirations.

Discourses within the early modern mining-industry indicate, however, that this new approach to language – in particular the question of the *use- and powerfulness of languages* (with a precise and highly differentiated vocabulary) in combination with the problem of *empty words* (which consequently need to be filled by empirical investigations) – was not merely an invention of philosophical minds, disconnected to the practical needs and desires of their times, but strongly influenced by the specific conditions of highly economized environments.⁹²

Almost a century before Francis Bacon's *Novum Organum* (1620) was issued, one of the most important authors in the history of montane-literature (*Bergbücher*), the renaissance-scholar and doctor of medicine Georgius Agricola (Georg Pauer) published his first major book *Bermannus; sive de re metallica* (1530)⁹³. His introduction begins with a general reflection about the "darkness" that had gotten ahold of the science of minerals and mining because scholars had thoughtlessly altered or replaced classical (Greek and Roman) designations while simultaneously forgetting or ignoring the materials those names originally referred to.⁹⁴ The "clarity" and "power" of many languages was, despite

⁹⁰ C. Taylor, *Quellen des Selbst. Die Entstehung der neuzeitlichen Identität*, Frankfurt/Main 2012, p.351ff.

⁹¹ J. Vogl, *Kalkül und Leidenschaft. Poetik des ökonomischen Menschen*, Munich 2002, p.51ff.

⁹² The strong interplay between practice and theory will become a characteristic feature especially of the soon to emerge montane sciences and academies – J. Vogel, *Aufklärung untertage: Wissenswelten des europäischen Bergbaus im ausgehenden 18. und frühen 19. Jahrhunderts*, in: H. Schleiff/ P. Konečný (Ed.), *Staat, Bergbau und Bergakademie. Montanexperten im 18. und frühen 19. Jahrhundert* (in: *Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte*, Supplement No. 223), Stuttgart 2013, pp.13-34, p.22f; P. Konečný, *Die montanistische Ausbildung in der Habsburgermonarchie, 1763-1848*, in: H. Schleiff/ P. Konečný (Ed.), *Staat, Bergbau und Bergakademie. Montanexperten im 18. und frühen 19. Jahrhundert* (in: *Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte*, Supplement No. 223), Stuttgart 2013, pp.95-125, p.101; P. Schimkat, *Kameralistische Naturforschung: Das mineralogische Lehrsystem von Abraham Gottlob Werner*, in: H. Schleiff/ P. Konečný (Ed.), *Staat, Bergbau und Bergakademie. Montanexperten im 18. und frühen 19. Jahrhundert* (in: *Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte*, Supplement No. 223), Stuttgart 2013, pp.231-250, p.243.

⁹³ M. Koch, *Geschichte und Entwicklung des bergmännischen Schrifttums*, Goslar 1963, p.31.

⁹⁴ G. Agricola, *Bermannus, sive de re metallica/ Bermannus oder über den Bergbau* (1530), in: H. Prescher (Ed.), *Agricola, Georgius: Ausgewählte Werke (AGA), Vol.2*, 1955, p.66 (own translation).

some recent improvements, lost in the course of this process – as was the “*knowledge of substances*”, because people had neglected their *senses* and their *intellect* to determine and refine the real matter of words. “*We should be ashamed*”, Agricola adds furiously, that we frequently read and use these designations while at the same time having no real knowledge about the substances they represent.⁹⁵ True knowledge about minerals and mining would be of “*extraordinary use*”, allowing not only for effective cures of the bodies of men but also strengthening the state (the ‘body’ of the prince)⁹⁶ of Saxony (against the Turks in particular).⁹⁷ As long as we are unable to adopt our scientific methods, however, the forces within the substances will stay hidden, and all our speeches will go on being mere “*empty words without any use*”.⁹⁸

Distance and profit - investing into silver-mines

At the times of Georgius Agricola, the Erzgebirge (where he had lived and studied most of his life) had become one of the early-capitalistic centers of Europe. The impressive dimensions of its mining sector were both a result and a cause (pull-factor) of large money-inflows that exceeded by far the financial possibilities of miners and local communities.⁹⁹ In consequence, a chasm emerged not only between labour and capital but *knowledge and capital*. Already at the end of the fifteenth century a growing number of share-holders no longer lived within the mining-towns, but were merely represented by local residents (serving as agents) or professional factors.¹⁰⁰ Princes, bishops, abbots, merchants, wealthy bourgeoisie, city councils (et cetera) from all parts of the Holy Roman Empire (and beyond) invested in so called *Kux*, i.e. mine share certificates that not only entitled for a – normally the 128th - share of profit but also compelled subsidies (*Zubusse*) when needed.¹⁰¹

A majority of these people had therefore neither personal experience nor particular knowledge concerning the montane-industry and were hence particularly vulnerable to deceptive and fraudulent behavior by members of the montane-community. Especially traders of *Kux* (so called *Kuxkränzler*) were regularly accused of cheating, spreading false

⁹⁵ Ibid., p.68 (own translation).

⁹⁶ T. Simon, Gute Policey. Ordnungsbilder und Zielvorstellungen politischen Handels in der Frühen Neuzeit, Frankfurt/Main 2004, p.209.

⁹⁷ Agricola, Bermannus, p.68 und p.155 (own translation).

⁹⁸ Ibid., p.69 (own translation).

⁹⁹ Th.G. Werner, Das fremde Kapital im Annaberger Bergbau und Metallhandel des 16. Jahrhunderts, in: Neues Archiv für sächsische Geschichte, Vol. 57, No. 2, 1936, pp.113-179, p.120.

¹⁰⁰ Laube, Studien, p.83.

¹⁰¹ Blaschke, Sachsen, p.161f.

rumors and selling overprized shares of (sometimes) already exhausted mines.¹⁰² But also foremen and miners were under suspicion of hiding and covering silver-ores for later (secret) exploits, instead making investors believe that the mines were exhausted (et cetera).¹⁰³

The economic circumstances described here,¹⁰⁴ the specific tension between economic interests on the one hand and problems of distance on the other, created a culture that was *obsessed with the surfaces and their signs* (indicating truth, status and identity, subterranean riches, contents of mountains and stones, motives of competitors, knowledge of agents etc.), as they were potentially not only leading the way towards aspired riches but also, for all the ones who were unable to read the signs properly, towards bankruptcy and disaster. It would therefore be a mistake to simply reduce the problem of *empty words*, as mentioned before, to a conflict between authors as Agricola and Scholasticism (while at the same time it would mean falling for modernist biases concerning the School – ignoring not only the positive qualities of scholastic reasoning (e.g. concerning economic thought)¹⁰⁵ but also, among others, the potential of its methodology to organize social hierarchies within a vast European network of universities and scholars).¹⁰⁶ Instead the *emptiness of words* is part of a bigger problem, linked to typical processes and elements of commercialization as can be found in the environments of late-medieval and early-modern mining-regions.

The problematic centerpiece in the above mentioned ‘*surface of signs*’ was, besides the *signs of nature* (which will be addressed later), the *written or spoken word*. One document which impressively illustrates this is today the oldest literary record of German Mining, the *Märe vom Feldbauer*^{107,108} dating back to the early fourteenth century (approx. 1330-

¹⁰² T. Asmussen, The Kux as a Site of Mediation: Economic Practices and Material Desires in the Early Modern German Mining Industry, in: S. Burghartz/ L. Burkhart/ C. Göttler (Ed.), Sites of Mediation. Connected Histories of Places, Processes and Objects in Europa and Beyond 1450-1650, Leiden 2016, pp. 159-182, p.174. – from the 1500s on it became custom that the Saxon Princes nominated official *Kuxkränzler* in order to fight this kind of activities. There remained however a huge black market in which myriads of illegal *Kuxkränzler* were doing their businesses – Köhler, Keime, p.78f.

¹⁰³ G. Agricola, Zwölf Bücher vom Berg- und Hüttenwesen (1556), Munich 1977, p.18ff.

¹⁰⁴ Conditions that should also be found in other – other times and other places - commercial centers as they are, compare the role of the Principal-Agent-Theorem in modern economics for example, very much characteristic for (proto-) modern economics in general.

¹⁰⁵ O. Langholm, Scholastic Economics, in: T.S. Lowry (Ed.), Pre-Classical Economic Thought, Boston, Dordrecht and Lancaster 1987, pp. 115-135.

¹⁰⁶ R. Schönberger, Artikel: Scholastik, in: N. Angermann (Ed.): Lexikon des Mittelalters, Vol. 7, Munich 1955, pp. 1522-1526, p.1522; It also important to emphasize that Georgious Agricolas thought and (scientific) methodology was strongly influenced by scholastic traditions – H.Nobis/ B.Fritscher, Mittelalterlich-scholastische Wurzeln der Mineralogie Georgius Agricolas, in: M.Folkerts/ S.Kirschner/ A.Kühne (Ed.), Pratum floridum. Festschrift für Birgitt Hoppe, Augsburg 2002, pp.325-358.

¹⁰⁷ Could be translated as “Tale of a Miner”. „Feldbauer“ respectively „veltbowere“ (compare the Heidelberg Manuscript) was a Middle High German term for ‚miner‘.

¹⁰⁸ Koch, Geschichte, p.15.

1350, author unknown).¹⁰⁹ Corresponding to the formal demands of its literary genre (*Mär/Märe*) this text is a short moral piece, warning feudal aristocracy about the dangers of engaging in the realm of commerce, respectively the mining-business, concluding with the *epimythion* that noblemen should rather be serving god as it is him alone who will eventually decide one's fortune. It is not, however, these rather conventional aspects of the storyline that are of interest here, but the idiosyncratic and vital *role of words* in the course of the narrative.

The story begins with some introductory words of the aristocratic narrator (and fraud victim): *"Listen up, you good people", I will tell you all about a person that fooled me, a person from which I was unable to protect myself, an individual that lied to me and tricked me, caressing me with "sweet words" of how rich he would make me – that person was a miner.*¹¹⁰ What follows is the tragedy of an investor who is *too distanced from the object of his commitment*, who knows little if nothing about mining, who is not adequately connected with experts or other investors who would share with him crucial information, and – one of the, as will later be discussed, tipping points of the story - who lacks the determination to visit the pit himself. He is hence *caught in a cosmos of words* (important detail: he is using the medium of the narrative himself, now addressing other investors stuck in a world of words) which betray him right from the beginning till the bitter end: warnings and rumors did not reach him, unknown stones and materials with *"strange names"* (presented to him by the miner) made him believe in hidden riches,¹¹¹ as did unverifiable assurances made by the miner about his trustworthiness¹¹², alleged witnesses on mining claims, or incessant and intricate¹¹³ references to god and faith. Rising doubts after weeks and months of unsuccessful mining and lessening resources were again smothered by *"sweet words"*¹¹⁴ and *"good advice"*¹¹⁵ - until eventually the last story in a row of stories reached him (even the bitter end presents himself in the form of fiction); the bad news (*"böse Märe"*) that the lode was exhausted (*"daß der Gang nun ganz aus wäre"*)¹¹⁶ and that all efforts, investments and hopes had been in vain.

This example gives a clear outline of the different aspects concerning the problem with the *emptiness of words*. On the one hand it seems, although not directly addressed, plausible to assume that this nobleman could not have altered the course of events by

¹⁰⁹ F. Kirnbauer/ K.L. Schubert, *Die Märe vom Feldbauer*, Vienna 1955, p.8.

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*, p.11, lines 1-29 (own translation).

¹¹¹ *Ibid.*, p.13, line 33 (own translation).

¹¹² *'If I will have to speak the truth / I am free of all falsehood'* – *Ibid.*, p.13, lines 64f (own translation).

¹¹³ First rhetorically used by the miners as an institution and guarantee of trust, later then as a means to emphasize the innocence of the miner as it was only gods will.

¹¹⁴ For example again in the middle part: *„As I heard these sweet words / coming from his mouth / I felt good again"* – *Ibid.*, p.21, lines 198-203 (own translation).

¹¹⁵ *Ibid.*, p.29, line 314 (own translation).

¹¹⁶ *Ibid.*, p.35, line 424 (own translation).

reading the pamphlets of scholastic authorities. This estimate is supported by the fact that the impotence of scholarly book-wisdom will eventually become a recurring topos of critique in the newly emerging (around the fifteenth century) genre of printed mining books, culminating in statements as can be found in the editor's note to Balthasar Rößler's *Speculum Metallurgiae Politissimum oder Hellpolierter Bergbau-Spiegel* (1700), claiming that traditional "scholarships and methodologies add nothing to the public good", Aristoteles and other (including contemporary) philosophers had left many writings about metals and minerals (et cetera), but most of their wisdom, as "they have not seen the things they talk of, have neither done good inquiries nor hence achieved a good science of things" is "mere speculation" and therefore "of no service" to the ones interested in the montane-business.¹¹⁷ On the other hand, strongly emphasized by the *Märe vom Feldebauer*, it becomes clear that the second part of the phenomenon of *empty words* concerns the interaction and communication within highly economized areas in general (and not only the disappointment concerning scholastic knowledge). The *words of the other(s)* become, under such competitive and highly individualistic circumstances as found in the mining-areas of the Erzgebirge, both a sphere of existential hints, information and, paradoxically, *a surface that, especially for investors not living on site, cannot be trusted* (it is surely no coincidence that for example Georgius Agricola devotes several passages of his famous *De re metallica libri XII* (1556), one of the most important mining-books in European history, to the question of whether mining was in fact a business of wretchedness and malevolence, an accusation apparently frequently raised by his contemporaries)¹¹⁸.

Piercing the surface of words: experiences on site

Much of the mining literature that was produced in the fifteenth and sixteenth century (and afterwards) can be regarded as a reaction to this two-sided (see above) struggle with the surface of uttered beliefs, promises, speeches, advises, written statements, prices, (for outsiders) cryptic miners-language (et cetera) – expanded by, as already implied, a third side: the equally difficult to decipher signals of nature, of silver, copper and other ores. Their art, their specific use and service to the reader (the term *use/useful* finds itself in the great majority of its titles) was hence to teach people interested in mining – not so much the practitioners themselves (as they had other means to pass on

¹¹⁷ J. C. Goldberger (Editor's Note), in: B. Rößler, *Speculum Metallurgiae Politissimum oder Hellpolierter Bergbau-Spiegel*, Dresden 1700 (own translation). This skepticism towards 'philosophical', that is abstract (book-) knowledge of unexperienced (concerning the day-to-day mining routines) scholars, will stay prominent also within the emerging montane sciences of the eighteenth century – P. Konečný, Kameralisten, Bildungsreformer und aufstrebende Bergbeamte: Johann Thaddäus Anton Peithner und sein Vorschlag zur Gründung einer Bergakademie im Habsburgerreich, in: M. Lacko (Ed.), *Montánna história / Die Montangeschichte*, No. 8-9, 2017, pp.66-89, p.71.

¹¹⁸ *Agricola*, Zwölf Bücher, pp.18-20.

this knowledge) but especially the unexperienced potential investors¹¹⁹ - *how to read the signaling surface and penetrate it in order to reach the hidden treasures underneath*.¹²⁰ However different these books were – some, as Agricola's works were very scientific in nature, others, as Johann Mathesius' *Sarepta* (1578) had a very folkloric character, others again, as Hans Rudhart's *Antzeigung des [...] Berckwergks Sanct Joachimsthal* (1523) functioned primarily as advertisements to attract foreign capital¹²¹ - they all aimed for (and exploited) the information deficits between the individual economic agent (above all potential investors) on the one hand and the signs of men and nature on the other.

Their distinctive reply to this problem was to emphasize the unconditional role of *knowledge* for successful investing in the mining-sector. 'I want', says Knappius, one of the two protagonists of the first ever printed mining book *Ein nützlich Bergbüchlein* (Ulrich Rülein von Calw, around 1500), "to thoroughly experience and learn with sense from this booklet which ore deposits can be exploited with success, so that my expenses will not be in vain but invested with profit".¹²² This statement can legitimately be understood as comprising the very essence of the mining literature of these centuries. Agricola (1556) and Biringuccio (1540) for example will both argue that although the influence of luck and chance for mining success cannot be entirely denied, it is not these circumstances, however, which will determine your fate, but experience, knowledge and science.¹²³ The ones interested in mining who have "little knowledge concerning the art of mining" will, although there are plenty of riches hidden (a typical argument of these authors, trying to engage outsider's – including potential investor's - attention), "soon impoverish" predicts Peder Månsson (the last in the row of the important *Bergbuch*-authors who shall be mentioned here) which motivated him to write this book in order for (potential) miners "to read it and to become knowledgeable".¹²⁴

The twice mentioned term *experience* indicates that the knowledge in demand here is of a specific type. The historian Petrus Albinus (Peter von Weiße) got to the heart of this spirit when he wrote in his *Bergk-Chronika* (1590), that "no one can properly write about things which he had not seen himself"¹²⁵, thereby not only mirroring a characteristic *empirical ethos* that can be found in most of the *Bergbücher* in consideration but also

¹¹⁹ H. Baumgärtel, Vom Bergbüchlein zur Bergakademie. Zur Entstehung der Bergbauwissenschaften zwischen 1500 und 1765/1770, Leipzig 1965, p.24/p.27.

¹²⁰ W. Eßbach, Der Bergbau und die Kultur des Findens, in: Österreichische Zeitschrift für Soziologie, Vol. 7, No. 1&2, 1982, pp.6-18.

¹²¹ Most of the mining books had this intention (among other motifs) – this also includes for example the first printed mining book from Rülein von Calw or even the scientific works of Agricola. Especially the introduction to *De re metallica libri XII* (1556) seems to be clearly intended to attract investors, in particular the Saxon Princes.

¹²² W. Piper, Ulrich Rülein von Calw und sein Bergbüchlein, Berlin 1955, p.115 (own translation).

¹²³ Agricola, Zwölf Bücher, p.1f; O. Johannsen, Biringuccios *Pirotechnia*, Braunschweig 1925, p.21.

¹²⁴ O. Johannsen, Peder Månssons Schriften über technische Chemie und Hüttenwesen, Berlin 1941, p.190f (own translation).

¹²⁵ P. Albinus, Meißnische Land- und Berg-Chronica, Dresden 1590, p.3 (own translation).

addressing a kind of epistemology that was thought to apply for *everyone* who was interested in true knowledge – that is to say in more than empty words - about mining issues.

A whole hierarchy of knowledge forms presents itself here. On the lowest level one finds the *knowledge of scholasticism* – especially early authors of the genre mention traditional authorities as references, as was official scholarly custom then, but either do (secretly) not make much use of this type of knowledge (as Rühle von Calw for example) and/or emphasize that old authorities like Plinius and others were not of much help for their scientific endeavor (like Agricola for example). Above this level ranks the *knowledge of specialists*, especially the one of miners and mining officials - frequently named by mining books as their main source (in order to legitimize one's own book), but also as important addresses to which potential investors should turn to in search for valid information. The highest form of knowledge however is the *experience gathered on site*, information gained (guided by the *useful* knowledge of the *Bergbücher*) in contact with the very substances, materials and practices of mining themselves.

The more literature and the economic logics of mining intertwined, the more this kind of knowledge-hierarchy became apparent. Already Albert the Great's (1193-1280) *De mineralibus* was, compared to its time, unusually rich with personal experiences and observations.¹²⁶ The same applies for Peder Månsson, a clergyman who was admittedly strong informed by scholastic dogmatism (grounding much of his *Bergbuch* on the works of Albert) but nevertheless known to be unconventionally interested in the practical arts.¹²⁷ Following these scholars, particularly Biringuccio's *Pirotechnia* and the works of Agricola took a next step, radically challenging traditional book-wisdom and putting experience and hands-on knowledge in the center of their scientific considerations.¹²⁸

If you want to get rich, if you want to pierce through the surface of signs, of empty and deceiving words as much as of the cryptic signs of nature then you need to learn to read them, you need to extinguish the distance between yourself and the object of your aspirations. "You will have", Biringuccio urges his readers, "to keep your eyes and ears open at anytime", "you will have to permanently look for signs [of ores] and you should try to collect as many hints as you can".¹²⁹ If you want to find the treasures of nature you will have to use all of your senses. Listen to what long-time residents and shepherds have to tell, Biringuccio wrote, taste rivers and creeks for bitterness, be alert to characteristic forms and deformations of the flora, watch out for the different colors of stones, use your

¹²⁶ Koch, Geschichte, p.11.

¹²⁷ Johannsen, Schriften, p.7.

¹²⁸ Ibid., p.21.

¹²⁹ Johannsen, Pirotechnia, p.10 (own translation).

olfactory sense to detect 'ore vapors' (et cetera) – so “that you will not squander your capital” by investing into fruitless sites and mines.¹³⁰ To this end it is of great importance to have gathered much experience – successful persons in the montane-business have (according to Agricola) the “greatest experience”, they don't rush but carefully take samples, they know how to read (and process) the landscape, the shape and orientation of hills and mountains, the texture of stones and soil but also (for example) the people that work for them. They visit the sites (of which they hold shares) frequently to gather information about the operations of the mine – if necessary staying on site for several days. And they do not hesitate to go down the pit as often as they can in order to gain personal insight into the situation underground.¹³¹

The question remains however, whether this *empirical ethos*, which came to prevail within the works and thoughts of mining-scholars, was in fact influential in the actual praxis of investors, of wealthy bourgeoisie, noblemen, princes and clergy buying and selling *Kux* in the Erzgebirge. While it is certainly appropriate to consider the perspective of the *Bergbücher* as an idealised one, there are nevertheless reasons to believe that this empiricist normativity was in fact strongly mirrored by the reality of the montane-business. On the one hand there is the aspect of the slow metamorphosis of montane-literature (as shown), intensifying its empiricist semantics the closer it got to the montane-economy itself. Famous investors like Martin Römer (d. 1483), a merchant from Zwickau who made approximately a 200,000 fl. profit by investing into Erzgebirge pits,¹³² were known to have a huge experience in the field of mining. His services especially as *Berghauptmann* (from 1474 on) for the Wettin Princes allowed him to visit many pits, thereby accumulating masses of empirical knowledge and maintaining a steady advantage of information over competitors.¹³³ It is very likely that such examples had a strong influence on the authors of mining books – in particular as they were often connected to these people and/or investing into mining-shares (like Ulrich Rülein von Calw for example) themselves. On the other hand there are some hints which suggest that a lot of these *Bergbüchlein* and authors were in return influential to the community of mining-investors. Besides the success of some of these books, the amount of editions that were printed and sold, there is amongst others evidence that even the Wettin Princes frequently visited the Erzgebirge and the mines they had invested in. Moritz Elector of Saxony for example spent between 1541 and 1551 more than 70 days in the Erzgebirge region, preferentially in the mining towns of Schellenberg, Zschopau,

¹³⁰ Ibid., p.10-12 (own translation).

¹³¹ Agricola, Zwölf Bücher, p.23.

¹³² J. Kahleyß, Der wirtschaftliche Aufstieg des Martin Römer, in: Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte, Vol. 100, No.2, 2013, pp. 154-177, p.158.

¹³³ Dietrich, Frühkapitalismus, p.46.

Marienberg and Annaberg.¹³⁴ Even if such behavior cannot simply be attributed to the guidance of mining-books and their scholars, it still proves that the idiosyncratic (economic) logics of the mining-sector and its characteristic demand for empirically backed information did not spare anyone interested in prevailing in its realm – even the Saxon Princes had to go through this *school of empiricism*.

4. Conclusion: Perspectives on a knowledge culture

Mining has always been a knowledge-intensive undertaking. Finding and smelting ores, stabilizing drifts, bailing inflowing waters – all these and other challenges did not only demand high levels of experience among the miners-community but also, from around the thirteenth century onwards, created a need for mining experts –most notably specialising in hydraulic engineering - who offered their services all over Europe.¹³⁵ And while there is still much controversy whether scientific knowledge played a major part in the course of the Industrial Revolution,¹³⁶ it is rather improbable that crucial developments within the mining-sector, at least from the sixteenth century onwards, could have taken place without it.¹³⁷ Although the knowledge of these days cannot be equated with modern scientific thinking, it would be, as already indicated by the tradition of the *Bergbücher* (and the outstanding works of Agricola amongst others), wrong to underestimate it. Following, as an example, the then establishment of the so called *Direktionsprinzip* (in the Erzgebirge as well as in the Harz for example), an early-absolutistic system of economic control and production, a community of highly educated bureaucrats came into existence, a class of hybrid “scientific-technical

¹³⁴ M. Wetzel, Der Erzgebirgische Kreis im Ausgestaltungsprozess des frühen albertinischen Territorialstaates, in: M. Schattkowsky (Ed.), Das Erzgebirge im 16. Jahrhundert. Gestaltwandel einer Kulturlandschaft im Reformationszeitalter, Leipzig 2013, pp. 33-44. p.42f; The visiting of mines and mining regions by the authorities was of course also connected to representative purposes – P.Konečný, Der Herrscher im Bergwerk. Visitationsreisen der Habsburger-Lothringer in die ungarischen (slowakischen) Bergreviere am Beispiel einer Reise von 1764), in: W.Telesko (Ed.), Die Repräsentation der Habsburg-Lothringischen Dynastie in Musik, visuellen Medien und Architektur (1618-1918), Wien/Köln/Weimar 2017, pp.346-366.

¹³⁵ Bartels/Klappauf, Mittelalter, p.243.

¹³⁶ Several works in the last two decades strongly emphasized the important role of (scientific) knowledge in the course of the Industrial Revolution – see for example J. Mokyr, The Gifts of Athena. Historical Origins of the Knowledge Economy, Princeton 2002; J. Mokyr, The Intellectual Origins of Modern Economic Growth, in: The Journal of Economic History, Vol.65, No.2, 2005, pp. 285-351; M.C. Jacob, The First Knowledge Economy, Cambridge (UK) and New York 2014.

¹³⁷ C. Bartels, Der Harzer Oberbergmeister Georg Andreas Steltzner (1725-1802) und die Montanwissenschaften in der zweiten Hälfte des 18. und am Beginn des 19. Jahrhunderts, in: H. Schleiff/ P. Konečný (Ed.), Staat, Bergbau und Bergakademie. Montanexperten im 18. und frühen 19. Jahrhundert (in: Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte, Supplement No. 223), Stuttgart 2013, pp. 275-288, p.276.

experts”¹³⁸ which would later, among others, form the intellectual basis for the first German university for mining affairs: the *Bergakademie Freiberg* (est. 1765).¹³⁹

In debates about the interrelation of knowledge and (modern) society it has become custom to focus on forms of knowledge which intuitively seem closely linked to industrial processes per se – as mechanical, chemical, physical, economical or comparable types of know-how. The research presented in this article offers a supplementary angle to these discourses by describing how processes of economization - *a process in the course of which evermore people, increasingly anonymous to each other, had to economically interact* - were able to change the epistemology of whole societies at certain times and places. Whether on the marketplaces or within the cosmos of mining-investors – the people of the Erzgebirge were confronted with problems of insufficient information, hence with questions of trust, risk and above all: knowledge. Seductive offers, hidden intentions, lies and rumors, hollow phrases, promises of riches – in these highly commercialized economic zones one had to, like William Petty and his contemporaries later on, learn to pierce through and therefore read the surface of (empty) words as much as one had to read the signs of nature. Empiricist ideals, the notion of useful knowledge, the rejection of scholastic authorities and book-wisdom, the emphasis on reliable personal experiences, the proclivity for practical and empirical rather than abstract philosophical theories – they flourished within these communities turning valid and useful knowledge into a highly relevant resource.

There is, however, an additional facet to this transformation that should be mentioned in the context of this article. Joel Mokyr, like many other authors dealing with the interrelation of knowledge and economy, uses the term ‘knowledge/useful knowledge’ in a very broad sense, including scientific as well as artisanal or other forms of knowledge.¹⁴⁰ Such a definitional decision allows him to conclude, for example, that today’s “societies ‘know’ more”, that processes of “*specialization, professionalization, and expertization*”, driven by and driving the western economies since the Age of Enlightenment, have eventually led to a situation in which “*the total amount of knowledge that society controls is vastly larger than ever before*”¹⁴¹. Such a use of the term “knowledge”, although one does not need to deny the general proposition of the statement, runs the risk of ignoring a very important transformation of the ‘shape’ of knowledge that has taken place in many societal realms over the last centuries – a metamorphosis that can

¹³⁸ U. Klein, *Nützliches Wissen. Die Erfindung der Technikwissenschaften*, Göttingen 2016.

¹³⁹ H. Schleiff, *Aufstieg und Ausbildung im sächsischen Bergstaat zwischen 1765 und 1868*, in: H. Schleiff/ P. Konečný (Ed.), *Staat, Bergbau und Bergakademie. Montanexperten im 18. und frühen 19. Jahrhundert* (in: *Vierteljahresschrift für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsgeschichte*, Supplement No. 223), Stuttgart 2013, pp. 125-160.

¹⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, S.139.

¹⁴¹ Mokyr, *Intellectual Origins*, S.287.

be perfectly observed in the example of the late-medieval, early modern mining region of the Erzgebirge.

This transformation could be described as, with metaphorical reference to the mining process, a gradual shift from *horizontal* to *vertical knowledge*. *Horizontal knowledge* stays within the same level of the order of things, of texts, collecting, commenting, (re-) combining and rearranging elements without trying to pierce through, leave or disrupt the common order. *Vertical knowledge*, in contrast, is highly selective, active and necessarily ignorant to many elements of its environment. It is designed to make a difference and condemned to produce unintended side effects. It opens up the circularity of orders and forces them into linear patterns.

Neither the people on the marketplace nor the investors in the Erzgebirge mining operations could reasonably expect to 'understand' the world in which they were engaged in, despite being heavily dependent on information about their environment to act successfully. *Empiricist semantics and strategies as well as a kind of (typically empiricist) restlessness – visiting places, moving around between market-stalls, testing options, listening to rumors, following intuitions etc. – that stood in stark contrast (and very much reflect Bacons vision of an active science) to the then still contemplative ideals of philosophy were only one side and one form of reaction to this problem. The other side, as we have seen for example in context of the marketplace, was to extremely narrow down and intensify one's focus and actions. Deep, vertical information relating to one's own operations was much more important than broad and undirected information – this also held true for the group of mining investors. One had to know how to only read the relevant signs: losing oneself in the 'horizontal' layer of reasoning and pondering, of all the information that could be gathered would mean risking one's velocity, the ability to act, the potential to bundle one's (knowledge) resources in few points and places in order to break through the order of things and find the hidden riches.*